

CURRICULUM CONTENT, SOCIAL AWARENESS AND COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT IN THE NEW NORMAL: INPUT TO THE ACQUISITION OF LEARNING COMPETENCIES OF GRADE 12 STUDENTS IN APPLIED ECONOMICS

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on the learning competencies and how curriculum content, social awareness and community involvement helped in gaining improvement in Applied Economics. It aimed to determine the importance of curriculum content, social awareness, and community involvement in acquiring inquiry skills, comprehension, and application. It also emphasizes the techniques of the teachers in teaching Applied Economics in gaining learning competencies. The results of the study revealed that the curriculum content, social awareness, and community involvement have a significant relationship with inquiry skills, comprehension and application in acquiring learning competencies. Based on the findings of the study, the following were hereby recommended: Since the study revealed that curriculum content, social awareness and community involvement help students in acquiring learning competencies, the school should prioritize the importance of the aforementioned factors to continuously improve the learning competencies of the students taking Applied Economics. Since the study revealed that the curriculum content, social awareness, and community involvement are important in acquiring learning competencies among Grade 12 students taking Applied Economics, the school should prioritize the organizations that patronize the importance of the aforementioned factors to contribute to the improvement of the students. It revealed that inquiry skills, comprehension and application improved by using curriculum content, social awareness, and community involvement. The school may support the teachers teaching Applied Economics to explore and participate to different community activities and social groups within the locality.

Keywords: curriculum content, social awareness, community involvement, applied economics, learning competencies, inquiry skills, comprehension, application.